

ASYMMETRIC ELASTIC-WAVE TRANSMISSION IN METACOMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

In this research, the development of a metacomposite structure is presented to realize asymmetric elastic-wave transmission in a broadband range. By virtue of the unique local resonance and the surficial localized vibrational modes in the proposed elastic metamaterial, multiple low-frequency asymmetric transmission bands (ATBs) can be easily achieved. Various kinds of periodic unit cells are designed to discuss the robustness of ATBs. The mechanisms of asymmetric transmission are theoretically and numerically investigated by both lattice and continuum models. The effects of dissipative oscillators on the ATBs are explored. Due to the merging effect induced by the dissipative dashpots, the bandwidths of ATBs in the metacomposite structure can be significantly broadened. Numerical and experimental verifications are conducted. The asymmetric transmission in time and frequency domains are further discussed. The proposed structure could be potentially beneficial for applications in elastic-wave control and directional transmission devices.

1 INTRODUCTION

The propagation of energy fluxes in conventional materials and structures is normally reciprocal and symmetric. Inspired by a great success in the development of electrical diodes, much effort has been devoted to realize the one-way propagation of different forms of energy flows. As a topic of particular recent interest, asymmetric manipulation of acoustic/elastic waves has attracted rapidly increasing attention due to the challenging one-way acoustic/elastic-wave transmission, as well as enormous application potential for various practical scenarios [1-6]. Various routes have been developed to obtain the asymmetric or unidirectional acoustic/elastic-wave transmission on basis of the nonlinear mediums, the biasing-based nonreciprocal devices or linear grating structures. However, the frequency bandwidths for asymmetric transmission in these structures are normally narrow, and the possibility to realize asymmetric elastic-wave transmission in multiple broadband frequency regions still needs more exploration. In addition, little work has been reported about the systematic study of damping effect on asymmetric wave transmission.

In this research, the development of a metacomposite structure is presented to realize asymmetric elastic-wave transmission in a broadband range. By virtue of the unique local resonance and the surficial localized vibrational modes in the proposed elastic metamaterial, multiple low-frequency asymmetric transmission bands (ATBs) can be easily achieved. Various kinds of periodic unit cells are designed to discuss the robustness of ATBs. The mechanisms of asymmetric transmission are theoretically and numerically investigated by both lattice and continuum models. The effects of dissipative oscillators on the ATBs are explored. Due to the merging effect induced by the dissipative dashpots, the bandwidths of ATBs in the metacomposite structure can be significantly broadened. Numerical and experimental verifications are conducted. The asymmetric transmission in time and frequency domains are further discussed. The proposed structure could be potentially beneficial for applications in elastic-wave control and directional transmission devices.

2 DESIGN AND RATIONALE

2.1 Metacomposite structure

The proposed metamaterial-based metacomposite structure is illustrated in Fig. 1. It consists of several periodical unit cells. Each unit cell is made up of three parts: outer shell, soft coat and inner cores. The outer shell and inner cores are made of relative “hard” metallic materials, and the soft coat is made of relative “soft” rubber materials. Two inner cores with different mass are included in each unit cell. In this research, four different design models of the two inner cores, as illustrated in Figs. 1(b)-1(e), are discussed and compared. For Model I (see Fig. 1(b)), each inner core contains only one hollow cylinder, which is named as one-resonator core; while for Models II and III, one of the two inner cores has one resonator, but the other one contains an additional cylinder inside the hollow cylinder, which is named as dual-resonator core. For Model IV, both inner cores are dual-resonator cores. The resonators are connected with each other by the soft materials between them, and the inner cores are connected with the outer shell also by the soft material.

Figure 1: (a) Schematic of the metacomposite structure and the unit cell of (b) Model I, (c) Model II, (d) Model III and (e) Model IV.

The material properties used in this research are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Material properties used in the continuum model [5, 6].

Material	Aluminum	Lead	Rubber
Young's modulus (GPa)	70	16	0.00078
Density (kg/m ³)	2770	11340	1200
Poisson's ratio	0.33	0.45	0.74

2.2 Effect of damping on ATBs

The proposed metacomposite structure can be analytically investigated by a dissipative diatomic mass-spring models, as shown in Fig. 2. The analytical transmission-frequency profiles can be obtained based on this lattice system, and similar mass-spring-damper models can be mimicked for different unit cells.

Figure 2: A linear diatomic mass-spring-damper model for the proposed structure.

Three damping coefficients ($\beta = 0$, 2×10^{-6} and 1×10^{-5}) are selected and the relevant asymmetric contrast ratios at a sweep frequency range are compared in Fig. 3. It is observed that merging and broadening effects on the ATBs are induced by increasing the damping coefficients. A series of discrete ultra-narrow ATBs are located around three main ATBs in the non-dissipative model, but they start merging with each other, also merging with their adjacent main ATBs with the increase of damping coefficients. The bandwidths of the main continuous ATBs have a significant improvement by virtue of the merging effect.

Figure 3: Effect of damping on the bandwidths of ATBs [6].

The detailed increment extents on the ATBs bandwidths are compared in Table 2. As much as 165.7 % increment is obtained by modifying the damping coefficients by considering contrast ratio $\psi = 0.4$.

Table 2. Effect of damping on ATB bandwidth improvement percentages

Rayleigh damping	ATB Bandwidth Improvement (%)		
	Continuum model		
β	1 st ATB	2 nd ATB	3 rd ATB
0	Baseline	Baseline	Baseline
2×10^{-6}	+1.3	+22.3	+170.0
1×10^{-5}	+29.1	+80.4	+165.7

2.3 Effect of damping on transient responses

One typical frequency, 1440.3 Hz, is further selected to analyze the transient responses along the two opposite directions. As exhibited in Fig. 3, the transmission characteristics along the opposite directions should be very similar at this frequency due to the almost-zero contrast ratio for the non-dissipative continuum model. In contrast, this specific frequency in the dissipative model is within to the ATB because of the damping's merging effects. A prescribed displacement with this frequency is applied to different ends of a continuum rod consisting of 100 unit cells, respectively, and capture the transient responses at a same distance from directions L and R . The normalized displacement-time profiles captured from the two directions in non-dissipative and dissipative models are depicted in Figs. 4(a) and 4(b), respectively.

Figure 4: Normalized displacement-time profiles obtained from two opposite directions in the (a) non-dissipative and (b) dissipative diatomic continuum models [6].

It is shown that the output displacement amplitudes along directions L and R are very similar for the non-dissipative model. On the contrary, in the dissipative model, the transmitted waves from direction R are much larger than the very weak waves travelling from direction L . It is therefore verified from the other side that the ATB bandwidths can be enlarged and further controlled by proper designing and tailoring the dashpot coefficients.

3 CONCLUSIONS

A dissipative elastic metamaterial structure with dual resonators is proposed in this research. On basis of the analytical investigation, numerical simulation and experimental verifications, the following conclusions can be drawn:

(1) Based on the proposed metamaterial structure, asymmetric elastic-wave transmission is obtained in multiple frequency bands. The influence of damping on the asymmetric transmission and ATB bandwidth is theoretically analysed by a lattice model. The increment and merging effects on the ATB bandwidths are observed.

(2) Numerical verifications by using both mass-spring system and continuum model are conducted. Excellent agreements between numerical and analytical results are obtained.

(3) Experimental verification in the dissipative elastic metamaterial is further conducted. Asymmetric elastic-wave transmission in the proposed structure is experimentally observed.

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